

NOTES

Ion-Activity and Mobility Ratio Measurements Across a Lithium Form of Clay Membrane

M. Adhikari and D. Ghosh

Measurements of ion-activity by clay membranes were performed by a number of workers^{1,2,3}. It is expected that membrane potential depends on temperature of pretreatment of particular clay and with increase in temperature of pretreatment porosity of clay membranes might change as a result electrochemical behaviour of membrane should change. This was also the anticipation of Altug and Hair⁴, in case of glass.

In expectation to this Li-form clay membranes from Padegaon (0-6") soil was prepared and heated to different temperatures. Membranes heated to $450 \pm 10^\circ$ and $550 \pm 10^\circ$ showed similar behaviour whereas those heated to $> 700^\circ$ showed high electrical resistance to measurements. Membranes heated to greater than 700° probably loses all its electrochemical properties due to change of clay crystal lattice.

Details of experimental procedure including membrane preparation, ion-saturation etc., are similar as described earlier².

All chemicals were of A.R. grade. Two tiny calomel electrodes having ± 0.2 mV asymmetry were used. Readings were noted with the help of a Leeds Northrup K₂ type

TABLE 1

H⁺ activity measurements with Padegaon $450 \pm 10^\circ$ heated clay membranes
Temp. = 24-25°

Form of clay membranes	Av. Potential in mV			
	$\cdot 0009$ m HCl	$\cdot 0027$ m HCl	$\cdot 0081$ m HCl	$\cdot 0243$ m HCl
Na	24.75	25.1	22.65	20.1
K	24.65	22.15	17.9	16.9
Li	28.9	20.25	20.0	18.4
E _{Th_{ee}} (25°)	(27.86)	(27.62)	(27.3)	(26.93)

1. C. E. Marshall, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1939, **43**, 1155.
2. S. K. Bose, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **37**, 365.
3. M. Adhikari, *ibid.*, 1961, **38**, 817.
4. I. Altug and M. L. Hair, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1968, **72**, 599.

potentiometer in conjunction with a Leeds Northrup galvanometer. Experimental results were recorded in the tables.

TABLE II

Na⁺ activity measurements with Padegaon 450 ± 10° heated clay membranes
Temp. = 23-24°

Form of clay membranes	Av. Potential in mV		
	<u>·009 m NaCl</u> ·003 m NaCl	<u>·027 m NaCl</u> ·009 m NaCl	<u>·081 m NaCl</u> ·027 m NaCl
Na	25.2	24.2	17.2
K	23.35	22.4	12.5
Li	26.75	26.35	23.9
E _{Theo} (25°)	(27.24)	(26.93)	(26.48)

TABLE III

K⁺ activity measurements with Padegaon 450 ± 10° heated clay membranes
Temp. = 25-26°

Form of clay membranes	<u>0.008389 m KCl</u>	<u>0.004989 m KCl</u>	<u>0.016 m KCl</u>
	0.005715 m KCl	0.001585 m KCl	0.004989 m KCl
Na	8.4	27.55	21.25
K	7.9	26.15	22.95
Li	9.9	28.5	28.3
E _{Theo} (25°)	(9.85)	(28.59)	(28.74)

TABLE IV

Ion-activity measurements with Li-Padegaon 550 ± 10° heated clay membranes

	Av. Potential in mV		
	<u>·009 m HCl</u> ·003 m HCl	<u>·027 m HCl</u> ·009 m HCl	
	18.4 (33°)	14.45 (33°)	
	<u>·009 m NaCl</u>	<u>·027 m NaCl</u>	<u>·081 m NaCl</u>
	·003 m NaCl	·009 m NaCl	·027 m NaCl
	26.75 (33°)	26.7 (31°)	22.65 (33°)
	<u>·009 m KCl</u>	<u>·027 m KCl</u>	<u>·081 m KCl</u>
	·003 m KCl	·009 m KCl	·027 m KCl
	28.3 (32.3°)	23.7 (30.7°)	22.25 (30.3°)
for I-I electrolyte at 30°	(27.8)	(27.4)	(26.95)

TABLE V

<i>U_H+/U_{Na}+ determinations</i>					
Temp. (30-31°)	Form of membranes	Inside soln. (Inside soln. +ve)	Outside soln.	Av. Pot. in mV	U _H +/U _{Na} +
(30.5°)	Li-550°±10°	·003 m NaCl	·003 m HCl	31.85	3.38
		·006 m NaCl	·006 m HCl	32	3.40
		·099 m NaCl	·009 m HCl	30	3.15
31°	Li-450°±10°	·006 m NaCl	·006 m HCl	36.1	3.97
		·009 m NaCl	·009 m HCl	36.5	4.03
<i>U_H+/U_K+ determinations</i>					
		Inside soln. (Inside soln. +ve)	Outside soln.	Av. Pot. in mV	U _H +/U _K +
30°	Li-550°±10°	·003 m KCl	·003 m HCl	18.35	2.02
		·009 m KCl	·009 m HCl	18.4	2.02
31°	Li-450°±10°	·003 m KCl	·00287 m HCl	14.4	1.84
		·009 m KCl	+·00287 m HCl	14.75	1.84
<i>U_K+/U_{Na}+ determinations</i>					
		Inside soln. (Inside soln. +ve)	Outside soln.	Av. Pot. in mV	U _K +/U _{Na} +
31.7°	Li-550°±10°	·003 m NaCl	·003 m KCl	15.3	1.791
31.6°		·006 m NaCl	·006 m KCl	17.7	1.963
31.4°		·009 m NaCl	·009 m KCl	18.3	1.99
30°	Li-450°±10°	·003 m NaCl	·003 m KCl	22.85	2.401
		·009 m NaCl	·009 m KCl	21.8	2.305

Results of our work have revealed that individual ion-activity measurements or mobility ratio determinations do not depend on temperature of pretreatment of clay membranes, but to an extent may depend on the nature of ion-saturation of clay.

Slight variations in values of ion-activity and mobility ratio measurements by 450±10°, 550±10°, heated clay plates may be due to the fact that in clay plates pore size cannot be controlled by temperature of pretreatment, and furthermore pores in clay plates are not of same radius. In clay plates pores are physical pores (unlike glass where pores are structural pores). Slight variations may then be attributed to unlike adsorption of ions (whose activity or mobility ratio is measured) on the walls of the pores. Hence it may be said that ion-specificity in clay membranes cannot be developed by changing temperature of pretreatment of clay but to a certain extent ion-saturation of clay prior to heat treatment may influence the ion-specificity of membrane.

Thanks are due to the Principal of Vivekananda Centenary College, Rahara R. K. M. Boy's Home for kind interest in this work.